

Occurrence of Rhazine in *Alstonia scholaris* R.Br.: Biogenetic and Chemotaxonomic Significance of the Co-occurrence of Several Indole Alkaloids Having a Common Structural Pattern

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Isolation and characterisation of rhazine from *A. scholaris* is described. Its role in the biogenesis of several alstonia alkaloids is discussed.

Earlier investigations on *Alstonia scholaris* R.Br. (*Apocynaceae*) have resulted¹ in the isolation of three indole alkaloids, viz., echitamine (IX), echitamidine (VIII), and picrinine (X).

The occurrence of another indole alkaloid, viz., rhazine, in the fruits and trunk-bark of this species is reported in this paper. Rhazine occurs almost ubiquitously² in the family *Apocynaceae* and thus occupies a key position in determining the inter-relationships of indole bases and their elaboration patterns.

Alcoholic extracts of the powdered defatted fruits and trunk bark of *A. scholaris* were processed separately, in the usual way, and the weakly basic constituents, as chloroform-soluble acetates, were kept aside for further treatment. The fairly strong basic fraction which remained in aqueous acetic acid solution was basified and the liberated bases were taken up in chloroform. The mixture of crude bases obtained upon removal of the solvent was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. The benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluates afforded a crystalline alkaloid (ca. 0.0005%), $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_3$ (M^+ , 352), m.p. 234–36°. It is a tertiary base (pK_a , 6.3) containing one –OMe, one –CMe, and two active H atoms. The I.R. spectrum of the compound showed $\lambda_{max}^{(Nujol)}$ 2.95, 3.01, and 5.75 μ , due, respectively, to –NH, –OH (hydrogen bonded), and –CO₂Me functions. The U.V. absorption spectrum $\lambda_{max}^{(EtOH)}$ 228 (log ϵ , 4.52), 278–80 (log ϵ , 3.85), and 293 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 3.71) is typical of indole alkaloids. The alkaloidal colour reactions: Hopkin-Cole, violet; Fröhde, blue; CAS, grey-green are also characteristic of a tetrahydro- β -carboline entity.

All the above properties of the alkaloid indicate its close similarity to rhazine (akuamidine)³ (XI). The identity was finally established from mmp. determination with an authentic sample, itself melting at 234°, which remained undepressed; co-chromatography on TLC using silica gel-G as adsorbent and methanol as developer, R_f , 0.64; superimposable I.R. spectrum; and identical mass spectral fragmentation pattern.

1. A. Chatterjee, B. Mukherjee, A. B. Ray, and B. Das, *Tetrahedron Letters* 1965, No. 41, 3633 and ref. cited therein.
2. J. E. Saxton in 'Alkaloids, Chemistry and Physiology', Ed. R. H. F. Manske, Vol. X, Academic Press, New York, 1968, p. 501.
3. (a) A. Chatterjee, C. R. Ghosal, N. Adityachaudhury and S. Ghosal, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1961, 1034.
(b) J. Levy, J. LeMen, and M. M. Janot, *Compt. rend.*, 1961, 253, 131.

The co-presence of echitamidine (VIII), echitamine (IX), picrinine (X), and rhazine (XI) in *A. scholaris*, having a common structural pattern (carbocyclic/heterocyclic E-ring being absent in all of them), is of much interest from the point of view of their biogenesis.

In this respect demethylidihydrocorynantheine (I), occurring in some *Aspidosperma* species, occupies a particularly interesting position since all the aforementioned bases can be simply derived from it or from its biogenetic precursor (II) following certain conventional reactions. The sequence of reactions envisaged in 'Scheme-A' would draw some obvious criticisms due to lack of direct evidence as to their validity. Nevertheless, the proposal is significant at least in one aspect, i.e., it emphasizes that these alkaloids owe their origin to a 'ring-E-opened' precursor (II) rather than to the rupture of a preformed pentacyclic ring (yohimbinoïd or heteroyohimbinoïd) system.

The occurrence of rhazine in *A. scholaris* lends further support to the observed division of the genus *Alstonia* into three clearly distinct categories⁵ so far as the alkaloid structural types are concerned. While, *A. scholaris*, *A. congensis*, *A. gillettii*, *A. angustiloba*, *A. neriifolia*, and *A. verticilloso* produce alkaloids of the type (VIII–XI), *A. constricta* produces only the well known pentacyclic bases, viz., alstonine, tetrahydroalstonine, and rauwolscine. *A. macrophylla*, *A. villosa* and *A. somerstensis* elaborate, on the other hand, mainly bisindole alkaloids.

It is worth contending that *Alstonia muelleriana* which produces the oxindole alkaloid (XII)⁶ bears a close relationship, at least on biogenetic grounds (Scheme-B), to the first group of *Alstonia* plants.

Despite the underlying similarity in the structural patterns (VIII–XI) and (XII) (differing only in the state of oxidation) and consequently the taxonomic closeness of *A. muelleriana* and the first group of the *Alstonia* plants, Saxton commented⁵ that 'the structure of Alkaloid-C suggests that it (*A. muelleriana*) may belong to none of these groups'.

In the event of the above hypothesis being proved correct it would help to solve the structural problems of the remaining *Alstonia muelleriana* alkaloids⁷.

4. Cf, also 'Biogenesis of Indole Alkaloids : A Common Hypothetical Route', A Chatterjee and S. Ghosal, *This Journal*, 1965, **42**, 123.
5. J. E. Saxton in 'Alkaloid, Chemistry and Physiology', Ed. R. H. F. Manske, Vol. VIII, Academic Press, New York, 1965, p. 162.
6. C. E. Nordman and K. Nakatsu, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 353.
7. R. C. Elderfield, *Am. Scientist*, 1960, **48**, 193.

SCHEME A

Hypothetical Route^a to the Genesis of Indole Alkaloids of A. scholaris

SCHEME B

Hypothetical Route to the Genesis of 'Alkaloid-C' in A. muelleriana.

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